

Porous Bioactive Glass Microspheres Prepared by Flame Synthesis

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ABSTRACT

Low cost processing method to prepare porous bioactive glass (BG) microspheres is presented. Glass powder with composition based on 45S5 BG and exhibiting irregularly shaped particles was fabricated by conventional melting. Glass powder was alkali activated to induce pore formation during the following flame synthesis step. Porous microspheres, with diameters ranging between 45 and 75 μm , were successfully prepared and characterized by X-ray diffraction, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, and scanning electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy. The porous bioactive glass microspheres are promising candidates for applications in bone regeneration, tissue engineering, and as carriers for controlled drug delivery.

The field of inorganic bioactive materials started in 1971 with the discovery of 45S5 bioactive glass (BG) by Hench et al. [1]. It is a special composition of silicate glass containing 45% SiO_2 , 24.5% CaO , 24.5% Na_2O , and 6% P_2O_5 , in wt.%. Bioactive glass is able to bond to bone tissue and stimulates bone regeneration by the release of Si, Ca, P ions [2, 3]. Due to the low specific surface area, and the lack of microporosity, the bioactivity of melt-derived glasses mainly depends on the SiO_2 content [4]. Microspheres possess several advantages compared to irregularly shaped materials; therefore, they have become important in many scientific fields, including biomaterials. They can be engineered and manufactured to be solid, hollow, or porous, which provides a larger surface area allowing for sufficient therapeutic coatings, an increase in degradation rate and beneficial ion release profile [5], or encapsulation of various biomedical relevant components [6, 7]. Recently, porous calcium phosphate glass microspheres were fabricated by Hossain et al. [6] via the cost-effective flame spheroidisation process. Careful selection of the glass, pore-forming agent, and a manufacturing method with the required processing window enabled the production of porous glass microspheres via a single-stage manufacturing process. Microspheres are already exploited in the pharmaceutical and health care industry. Precise control over pore size is, however, difficult; hence, manufacturing technologies need to be improved to create reproducible porosity and pore sizes [7]. In the present study, a simple, cost-effective, and scalable method for the preparation of porous 45S5 BG microspheres is presented and discussed.

Bioactive glass of 45S5 composition was prepared by mixing the analytical grade purity ($\geq 99\%$) raw materials: SiO_2 , CaCO_3 (Centralchem, Slovakia), Na_2CO_3 (Penta, Czech Republic), and $\text{Na}_5\text{P}_3\text{O}_{10}$ (Sigma-Aldrich, Slovakia). The mixture was then melted in Pt-10% Rh crucible in a superkanthal furnace at 1300°C for two hours in ambient atmosphere. The homogeneity was ensured by repeated hand mixing of the melt. Then the molten glass was poured onto a stainless steel plate. The sample was tempered in a muffle furnace for 30 minutes at 560°C and then the furnace was switched off. The prepared bulk glass was crushed and sieved through a $45\ \mu\text{m}$ analytical sieve. The powder was mixed into an aqueous solution containing 1 M NaOH (reagent grade, Sigma Aldrich, UK), with a solid loading of 65 wt%. The glass powder was subjected to an alkaline attack for 1 h under mechanical stirring at 500 rpm. After alkaline activation, the obtained suspension of glass powders, subjected to surface dissolution, was cast in closed polystyrene cylindrical moulds

and cured at 75°C for 24 hours. Finally, the hardened gel was crushed and sieved through analytical sieves to obtain a fraction of 45-75 µm in size.

The precursor, prepared by the alkaline activation process, was fed into an oxygen-methane torch with a vacuum powder feeder using oxygen carrier gas. The spherical melt particles were formed in the flame with the estimated maximum temperature in the range of 1500-1600°C (which was measured in the centre of flame by a thermocouple) and then quenched by distilled water to form porous microspheres. The obtained spherical particles were separated from the distilled water by microfiltration through a ceramic filter with the pore size less than 0.3 µm.

To the best of our knowledge the paper presents the first successful preparation of porous bioactive (Figure 1) glass microspheres based on 45S5 BG composition by flame synthesis process. The microspheres were prepared by alkaline activation of conventionally melted BG powder, followed by flame spheroidisation. C-S-H and natrite, formed during the alkaline activation release volatile species (water vapour and CO₂) during the flame synthesis, which act as pore forming agents yielding to porous microspheres with diameter ranging between 45 and 75 µm. Only slight reduction in the content of Na₂O, P₂O₅, and CaO was observed after the flame synthesis.

Figure 1: Morphology of the as prepared porous 45S5 BG micro-sphere particles.

Keywords: Bioactive glass, porous microspheres, alkaline activation, flame synthesis.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

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